

ORGANISATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS IN PRIVATE INSTITUTIONS OF HIGHER EDUCATION: UNRAVELING THE DIMENSION OF EXCELLENCE

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Abstract:

Private institutions of higher education contributes immensely to the national development through deliberate preparation of human resource personnel. As private education struggles in the face of keen competition from public universities to fulfill their mission and mandate, the concept of organizational effectiveness becomes the focal point. This paper analysed data collected from 130 respondents comprising students, alumni, faculty and administrative staff of private institution of higher education. Analysis was done in descriptive framework using a descriptive statistics as techniques of analysis. The findings revealed that the overall organisational effectiveness was high ($\bar{x} = 3.77$). The study recommended that private university administrators should focus on resource acquisition and quality of teaching and research as a yardstick to again institutional effectiveness.

Key Words: Private Institutions of Higher, Organisational Effectiveness, Excellence

Introduction:

Private institutions of higher education are crucial in shaping national development. Private universities have mandate to provide student the needed training and education to make them useful for agents of development. To maintain their stand to properly discharge their mandate, these institutions have to prioritize organizational effectiveness in terms Organisational resources, quality of teaching and research, human resource production and international outlook. This paper aims to explore key areas of organisational effectiveness university leadership can leverage on to again competitive advantage for an enhanced organisational sustainability.

Review of Literature:

Many scholars see and conceive organisational effectiveness from different points of view. The effectiveness becomes relative in terms of time, spatial and environment. Cameron and Quinn (1983) identifies that organisational effectiveness is the proficiency of an organisation at having access to the essential resource. Vinitwanakhun (1998) in his study summarizes organisational effectiveness as a focus on human resources and organisations and helping individual to achieve skills and self-esteem in order to control the new environment and find security and support. From Vinitwanakhun view point, organisation's effectiveness should have a core strategy to consider the organisation objectives and alignment of relevant skills and talent to propel the achievement of those objectives.

This marriage between organisational objectives and skillful workforce is done through deliberate effort to help acquire relevant skills and self-empowerment needed to control the business environment to the advantage of the individual worker and organisations as a whole. Organisational effectiveness comprises the actual productivity of an organisation, in relation to intended outputs, goals and objectives.

On the other hand, McCann (2004) sees organisational effectiveness as a criterion of the organisations successful fulfillment of their purpose through core strategies. On the contrary, Federman (2006) sees organisational effectiveness as issues that concern the ability of an organisation to access and absorb resources for optimum utilization for the achievement of organisational aims. This means that organisational effectiveness is the extent to which an organisation as a social system, given certain resources and means, fulfills its objectives without in- capacitating its means and resources and without placing undue strain upon its members.

From the above scholarly definitions, organisation's effectiveness embraces availability of both material and human resource capable of aiding the achievement of the organisational objectives. It covers implementation of core strategies and proficiency of resources. Gavrea et al (2011) asserts that organisational effectiveness consists organisation – financial performance (return on investments, profits etc.), shareholder return (economic value added, total shareholder etc.) and the product/service market performance (market share, sales etc.). Therefore, many organisational leaders may tailor their effectiveness strategy to embrace their financial fortunes, markets performance and returns on shareholder investment. The way business leaders conceive organisational effectiveness informs their effectiveness strategy.

The effectiveness of institutions of higher education may be determined by their international outlook, resources, quality teaching and research as well as human resource production among others. Organisational effectiveness is a subject experiencing a lot of debate on its concept definition and approach. Kavagoz and Oz (2008) postulate that research on organisational effectiveness started as far back as the 1930s, receiving a lot of attention in the 1970s onward. Several scientific and management scholars have contributed to giving meaning to organisational effectiveness. Frederick Taylor who lived between 1865- 1915 identified in 1911 that organisational effectiveness was evidenced by variables consisting: production maximization, cost minimization and technological excellence.

These influential variables- product maximization, cost minimization and technological excellence- among other factors are used as indicators in measuring organisational effectiveness. An organisation's ability to increase production by delivering high quality service or product that meet the desire of customers or consumers is the first indicator of organisational effectiveness. An increase in production must be done efficiently and effectively at a minimal production cost using suitable and excellent technology. Though increased production by the use of high excellent technology at a minimized cost is key to achieving organisational effectiveness, other intervening variables like leadership, expertise of workers, some internal and external variables may also influence the organisational effectiveness. Henry Foyal who also lived between 1841 -1925 also contributed to understanding organisational effectiveness. He highlighted clear authority and discipline as major determinants of organisational effectiveness.

Foyal's assertion places organisational effectiveness at the door steps of leadership positional power, establishing clear authority in terms of provision of resources, task structuring and supervision of subordinates in attempt to achieve effectiveness. In all of the above, comes discipline both on the part of leadership and subordinates. Elton Mayo who lived between 1880s - 1949 also adds to the expansion of organisational effectiveness. He indicates the essence of productivity and employee satisfaction to organisational effectiveness.

The argument of Mayo is that an organisation's achieving effectiveness is all about productivity which stems from employee satisfaction (Robbins 2005; Scott & Peter, 2009). Despite the contributions of the above scholars, several other scholars have also organized studies into organisational effectiveness: Yuchtman & Seashore (1967) - Goals and systems approach to organisational effectiveness, Cameron & Whelton (1983) - Multi - dimensional models of organisational effectiveness and Quinn & Rohrbaugh (1981) - Competing values.

Organisational Effectiveness Models for Higher Education Institutions

There is a plethora of studies concerning effectiveness of educational institutions and the factors affecting effectiveness, however, the actual interpretation and use of the knowledge is limited because practitioners have not translated the findings of the studies into organisationally based action because of the differences in the institutional operations, size and vision. A lot of indicators similar in nature have been adopted in measuring organisational effectiveness in privately owned colleges and universities. Some studies on organisational effectiveness in colleges and universities are as follows:

Antia and Cuthbert (1976) organized a study on the success factors of polytechnics and in qualitative model suggested nine critical factors that determined the effectiveness of educational institutions. They indicated that these success factors are closely related to each other and therefore the neglect of one affects the other in the long term. The identified variables are: Social tune, Cost effectiveness, Course development, Cooperate reputation, Investment in human capital, Physical facilities development, Student relations, Quality of employee relations and Public responsibility.

Ashraf and Kadir (2012) assert that it is necessary to spot and comparatively emphasized by all institutions because the achievement of success in the nine areas is key to growth and effectiveness. Institutions must be socially tuned by mounting courses and programmes that meet the demands of industry. However, that must be done considering cost effectiveness in all of the institutions activities. Once the business environment is exacerbated by several changes, institutions must constantly develop new courses and invest in human capital to give them the needed expertise to hand new courses whiles developing physical facilities to help the cogent delivery of new programme. Educational institutions must be interested in enhancing good student's relations and quality employee relations in order to allow for tranquility in the institutions environment with the sense of corporate reputation and responsibility towards the public. Any educational institution that is able to handle or satisfy all these constituencies is rated effective.

Cameron (1978) in his study proposed organisational effectiveness model for 4 year colleges using 57 item questionnaires which were perception based on the effectiveness of institutions. He came up with nine indicators that influence institutional effectiveness: student educational satisfaction, student academic development, student career development, student personal development, faculty and administrator employment satisfaction, professional development and quality of faculty, system openness and community interaction, resource acquisition and organisation health.

According to Cameron (1978) the above constituencies are vital for any institutions survival and agility. Ashraf and Kadir (2012) add that base on Cameron's models, it is important for all contextual factors to be considered before organisational effectiveness criteria is selected. To compare other models of effectiveness

in higher education to that of Cameron, there is no much deviation. Most identified criteria or factors are similar and geared towards the same purpose. However, the application of any of these models to any educational institution may depend on myriad situational variables like demography, economics, government policy, technology among others.

Kleeman and Richardson (1985) in a study on student characteristics and perception of university effectiveness in three public universities in Arizona, identify 10 factors that determine effectiveness of education institutions: Programmes and service for students, Attention to women and minorities, Quality of teaching and research, Publication of knowledge and research, Workshops and Counseling to broaden access, Sports , Focus on cultural activities, Programme for graduates, Leasing facilities and Enhancement of standards.

The proper consideration of the ten determinants in decision making was seen as factors that yielded institutional effectiveness. Though the model proposed by Kleeman and Richardson (1985) looks very different and comprehensive to that of Antia and Cuthbert (1976) some of the success factors may be interrelated or yield similar outcomes. The study of Kleeman and Richardson (1985) concluded that among the ten factors stipulated, quality of teaching and research and programmes for graduates are most necessary to respondents and therefore must be given all the attention it desires.

Pounder (1999) in a study on “organisational effectiveness in higher education” in Hong Kong educational institutions established nine factors that influence the effectiveness of institutions. The study was done in 7 institutions with administration and academic staff as study group. The nine factors included: Productivity efficiency, Quality, Cohesion, Adaptability readiness, Information management – communication, Growth, Planning – goal setting, Human resource development and Stability control. The study concludes that among the nine factors in the model, planning and productivity triggered the effective performance of universities in Hong Kong. A firm grips on these areas better the chances of institutional survival.

An, Yom & Ruggiero (2011) studied into how organisational culture and quality of work life influence organisational effectiveness in Korean University hospitals. Their study evaluates organisations effectiveness at two levels: Job satisfaction and Organisational involvement. In the study, the factors that promoted organisational effectiveness were: Quality of career, Good organisational culture and Care (Salanke ,2014).

Salanke also studied into organisational effectiveness in higher education of Polytechnics in Nigeria. Salanke (2014) used three models to assess the effectiveness of the university with different indicators. The Human relations model had the following indicators: Staff training and development, Remuneration and campus relationship. The open system model had the following indicators: Acquisition of resources, Physical infrastructure and equipment’s and Accreditation. The rational goal model has only one indicator: strategic planning.

Internal Process model has the following indicators: accountability, internal resources allocation and information communication technology. Through the application of different models, Solanke (2014) highlight ten factors that influence higher education in Nigeria. The ability of any institution to respond adequately to these evaluated criteria assumes institutional progress and agility. The criteria include staff remuneration, campus relationship, resource acquisition, physical infrastructures and equipment, accreditation, strategic planning, accountability, internal resource allocation and information communication technology

Research Methodology:

The study used both primary and secondary data. The primary data were gathered through questionnaire administration in order to explore the state of organisational effectiveness in private universities or institutions of higher education. Questions on organisational effectiveness were responded to in order to determine the degree of perception of respondents. Data were processed using SmartLPS3 software. The research design for the study was survey using quantitative technique.

Total population of 130 respondents was involved in the study covering the junior staff members (25), alumni (5) and continuing students (100) from a private university in the Accra Metropolis using Stratified random sampling to select respondents.

Empirical Results:

To explore the state of organisational effectiveness, respondents had questions to rate the University international outlook, resources, quality of teaching and research and human resources production to measure the state of organisational effectiveness in private institutions of higher education.

Descriptive Statistics of State of Organisational Effectiveness:

Organisational Effectiveness Components	Mean(SD)	Interpretation
Resources (Scale Item)	4.0538(.73758)	High
This college can obtain raises easily financial resources for quality educational programme.	3.92(.932)	
This college has all the resources for effective education delivery.	4.18(.876)	
This college attracts the best faculty in the country.	4.07(.855)	
University’s International Outlook	3.8400(.61727)	High
The college has stimulating intellectual environment.	3.57(.980)	

The college has the reputation of concern for student development.	3.94(.842)	
This university is highly responsive and adaptive strategy needs of the external academic community.	4.14(.904)	
The college attracts the best students outside the country.	3.94(.869)	
Quality Teaching and Research	3.7167(.72087)	High
With regard to the academic level of achievement, last year's graduating class at this university was the top university graduating classes in the country.	3.85(.968)	
A great majority of the graduates from this university go on to obtain degrees in graduate or professional schools.	3.73(.922)	
Student activities outside the classroom are designed specifically to enhance students' academic development.	3.80(.927)	
Faculty members and/or administrators provide professional activities outside the regular university assignments.	3.75(.856)	
Almost half of the faculty members teach very well - i.e., require current journal articles as reading, revise syllabi at least yearly, discuss current issues-in the field, etc.	3.58(1.025)	
The majority of the faculty members at this college are actively engaged now in professional development activities, example doing research.	3.59(.970)	
Human Resource Production	3.6262(.66514)	High
One of the outstanding features of this college is the opportunity it provides students for personal development in addition to academic development.	3.52(.908)	
When hiring new faculty members, the college employs people in the country in their respective fields.	3.50(.909)	
Career development services are available for students at this college.	3.52 (.934)	
Majority who graduated from the college last year and entered the labor market have obtained employment in their major field of study.	3.66 (.803)	
The majority of the faculty members and administrators at this college attended a conference or workshop specifically oriented toward and/or personal development yearly.	3.94 (1.133)	
Note: N = 130		Min. = 1, Max.= 5

Source: Author's Construct, 2022

The Overall Org Effectiveness	Mean	Std. Deviation
Valid N (list wise) = 130	3.7785	.53988

Scale (Mean): 1-2.4=Low, 2.5-3.4=Moderate, 3.5-5.0 = High (Oxford &Stock, 1995)

Source: Author's Construct, 2022

With respect to the Table, the state of organisational effectiveness, the overall performance was high ($\bar{x}$ = 3.77). The desire of leadership to acquire resources for the daily operations of the university was also high ($\bar{x}$ = 4.05). As indicated in the Table, the international outlook of the university ($\bar{x}$ = 3.84) quality of teaching and research ($\bar{x}$ = 3.71) and human resource production ($\bar{x}$ = 3.60) were high. Organisational resources, quality of teaching and research, human resource production and international outlook or image of higher institution of learning are powerful indicators of organisational effectiveness. All these variables demonstrate positive correlation to organisational effectiveness and therefore cannot be taken for granted for the role they play in the performance of successful organisations.

Mwai et al (2012) from a study on the influence of organisational resources on organisational effectiveness finds that the resources of organisations are positively and significantly related to organisational performance and goals. They highlight that fundraising efforts which also has a positive influence on organisational processes must be rigorous in order to acquire relevant resources for the operational needs of organisations. This assertion by Mwai et al (2012) support the findings of this study which indicates resources with the high mean score ($\bar{x}$ =4.05) influences organisational effectiveness. This indeed juxtaposes that the University College leadership was working hard to give the institution a competitive advantage and to remain in business in order to deliver on its core mandate as a teaching University.

Maritan and Peterat (2016) support this finding by indicating that firms and organisations invest in resources with the aim to subvert or dodge market failures so as to increase their capacities to workable competitive advantage which is crucial to the survival of every business. Therefore, the prompt acquisition of resources by leadership of the university is crucial to the formidability and sustainability of the university

though other challenges may seem to derail the efforts of the resource investment.

Quality of Teaching and Research:

Teaching and research in universities depend on the type of faculty in relation to the experience and academic qualifications. From the Table, quality of teaching and research in was high ($\bar{x}$ =3.71).

The study reveals a total of 28 faculty members in the University College. Akplu (2016) argues that wide variations of quality of equity in private institutions are a major concern. He emphasizes that 23% of faculty members in private universities have terminal degrees but some of these private institutions do not have the terminal degree holders at all. The findings of the study is in consonance with the observations of Akplu (2016) as only 7.2% of the faculty members hold terminal degrees with 71.4% holding second degree with 21.4% holding below second degree qualifications.

Faculty Academic Qualifications:

The experience and quality of faculty members impact teaching and research as well as publication capabilities of universities. It is important for private tertiary institutions to have a plan to produce their own terminal degree holders as the supply of qualified faculty cannot increase to match demand (Akplu, 2016). Though the highest percentage of 71.4% of the faculty do not have terminal degree as indicated in Figure above, respondents insisted that the quality of teaching was good.

International Outlook:

Majority of the administrative staff revealed that 20% to 25% of the student population was foreigners or international students. This indeed gives the university good international outlook and presence which was high ($\bar{X}$ =3.84) as indicated in the Table. Akplu (2016) on the contrary finds out in his study that in 2012- 2013 academic year, international students in private universities stood at 12.6% of the total student enrollment in Ghana compared to 2% of the public universities. This indicates that majority of international students in Ghana were in private universities. This is critical to the success of the university because it is the major source of income. That will also mean that the university must roll out academic programme diversification that caters for the need of the wider global society. Akplu (2016) juxtaposes that among the top most concerns of private universities in Ghana is the quality of diverse human resources for the delivery of quality teaching and learning which most private tertiary institutions are struggling to meet.

Human Resource Production:

Tertiary institutions exist not only for knowledge production but for human resource production with requisite knowledge and skills needed for industrial and national development. From the Table, the human resource production was high ($\bar{x}$ =3.62). It is the engine of growth for the supply of manpower to feed development agenda of a nation.

Summary and Conclusion:

The study revealed that the state of Marshalls University College effectiveness was high in relation to examining the variables: resources, international outlook, teaching and research and human resource production though only 7.2 % of faculty and administrative staff members had terminal degrees.

The state of organisational effectiveness that is the overall performance was high ($\bar{x}$ =3.77). The desire of leadership to acquire resources for the daily operations of the university was also high ($\bar{x}$ =4.05). The international outlook of the university ($\bar{x}$ = 3.84), quality of teaching and research ($\bar{x}$ =3.71) and human resource production ($\bar{x}$ =3.60) were high. Organisational resources, quality of teaching and research, human resource production and international outlook or image of higher institution of learning are powerful indicators of organisational effectiveness.

References:

1. Cameron, K. (1978). Measuring organisational effectiveness in institutions of higher education, *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 23, 604-632. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/2392582>
2. Vinitwatanakhun, M. W. (1998). Factors affecting organisational effectiveness of nursing institutes in Thailand. 1-5. [Online] Available: <http://www.journal.au.edu/au techno/2002/apr2002/article8.pdf>.
3. Federman, M. (2006). Essay: Towards an effective theory of organisational effectiveness. http://whati sthemessage.blogspot.com/2006_03_01 archive.html.
4. Gavrea, C., Iliies, L. &Stegerean, R., 2011. Determinants of organisational performance: The case of Romania. *Management & Marketing*, 6(2), pp. 285-300.
5. Robbinson, L. P. (2009). The Implications of Transactional and Transformational
6. Leadership for Individual, team, and Organisational Development. <http://www.ijrcm.org/articles/cm3.ht>. Accessed 26 June 2012.
7. Scott, M. H and Peter, W.(2009). Empirical Investigation of the Effects of Transformational and Transactional Leadership on Organisational Climate. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 4, 16-18.
8. Quinn, R. E. and J. A. Rohrbaugh (1981). A competing values approach to organisational effectiveness. *Public Productivity Review* 5: 122-140.

9. Antia, J. M., & Cuthbert, R. E. (1976). Critical success factors in Polytechnic performance. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 5(14), 14-36. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/174114327600500103>
10. Kleeman, G. L., & Richardson Jr, R. C. (1985). Student characteristics and perceptions of university effectiveness. *Review of Higher Education*, 9(1), 5-20.
11. Pounder, J. (1999). Organisational effectiveness in higher education. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 27(4), 389-400. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0263211X990274006>
12. Solanke, A. O. (2014). Organisational Effort in High education: A case study of selected polytechnic in Nigeria. Doctoral thesis Southampton Education School.
13. Akplu H. F. (2016). Achievements and challenges of private higher education: University World News. The global window on higher education (Accessed January 4, 2022)
14. Maritan C. A. & Peteraf, M. A. (2011). Building a bridge between resource acquisition and source accumulation: *Journal of Management* Volume 37 Number 5.